

Evaluation of Carbon Stock of *Eucalyptus Camaldulensis* and *Azadirachta indica* Plantations

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SUMMARY

This study aimed to assess the carbon stock of Neem and river red gum tree plantations at Aliko Dangote University of Science and Technology (ADUSTECH) in Wudil. Permanent plots measuring 20 m² were established, with five random plots selected from each plantation (*Eucalyptus Camaldulensis* and *Azadirachta indica*). Measurements were taken for the total tree height and diameter at breast height (DBH) of all trees within the plots. The densities of the two species were determined by sampling three different trees, cutting them into rectangular shapes, and oven-drying them in the lab to calculate fresh volumes and final dried weights. Allometric equations developed by Chave et al. (2005) were used to determine the above-ground biomass (AGB), with below-ground biomass estimated at 26% of AGB. Estimated carbon and carbon dioxide sequestration were calculated as 47% of biomass, with a factor of 3.67 for carbon stored. The results indicated that the river red gum monoculture plantation achieved an average carbon stock of 172.32 tC/ha, with values ranging from 15.48 to 493.78 tC/ha, while the Neem plantation had a mean of 67.83 tC/ha, ranging from 13.46 to 209.77 tC/ha. Overall, the river red gum plantation demonstrated a superior capacity for atmospheric carbon reduction, highlighting its greater importance for carbon sequestration compared to Neem.

Keywords: Carbon, Biomass, *Eucalyptus Camaldulensis*, *Azadirachta indica*

INTRODUCTION

Globally, the detrimental effects of climate change and greenhouse gas emissions have become one of the most significant issues and topics of discussion today. These factors play a crucial role in temperature changes at the international level. Trees act as a sink for CO₂ by capturing carbon during the photosynthetic process, and the stored carbon remains as biomass (Nunes et al., 2020).

Tropical savannah is a major component of global vegetation, covering one-sixth of the land mass and accounting for 30% of the primary production of all terrestrial vegetation. By far, Africa contains the largest areas of savannah, with about 50% of the African land area (Williams et al., 2022). Furthermore, tropical forests play a vital role in global carbon recycling (Goodman, and Herold, 2014). They harbor about 40% of the world's terrestrial carbon, which accounts for more than half of global gross primary productivity, and sequester large amounts of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere (Beer, 2010). Carbon is stored in forests predominantly in live biomass and in soils, with smaller amounts in coarse woody debris (Campbell et al.,

2018). In tropical forests worldwide, about 50% of the total carbon is stored in aboveground biomass and 50% is stored in the top 1 m of the soil (Ngo et al., 2013).

Most of terrestrial carbon storage is in tree stems, branches, foliage, and roots which are called biomass. Forests carbon sequestration ability is higher than any other terrestrial ecosystem and is an important natural “brake” on climate change (Hari and Tyagi, 2022). The world forest sequester and store more than 650 billion tonnes of carbon, 44% in the biomass, 11% in dead wood and litter and 45% in the soil (FAO, 2010). The biomass of a tree is proportional and directly related with the size of some morphological characteristics of the tree. This relationship, otherwise called ‘allometry, can be described in equations, which allow the biomass to be estimated by supplying the equation with measurements of some parts of the tree. For instance, the diameter of the trunk (measured as diameter at breast height; 1.3 m DBH) has been found to be highly correlated with the total aboveground biomass (Walker et al., 2016). Allometric equations provide a means of estimating the biomass of individual trees of all sizes within the population from measurements of three dimensions. The development and application of allometric equations is the standard methodology for aboveground tree biomass estimation (Sebrala, 2022).

This study emphasized the comparative assessment of the carbon sequestration potential of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* and *Azadirachta indica* plantations, utilizing two carbon pools: aboveground biomass and belowground biomass. As climate change and global warming persist in jeopardizing the earth's ecosystem balance, it has become more crucial to find methods to reduce the impact of greenhouse gas emissions.

The results of this research may provide guidance to policymakers and decision makers regarding reforestation and afforestation initiatives in Nigeria and other comparable areas with similar ecological characteristics. Although *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* and *Azadirachta indica* are significant, information on their capacity for carbon sequestration is scarce. Consequently, this research will help bridge the gap and offer valuable insights into the condition of these species. The research seeks to assess the carbon storage of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* and *Azadirachta indica* plantations. In particular, the primary goals of this research paper are to assess and contrast the carbon stock of *Azadirachta indica* and *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* plantations, as well as to establish the above and below ground biomass of both *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* and *Azadirachta indica* plantations.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

RECONNAISSANCE VISIT

A reconnaissance visit was carried out to identify some basic characteristics of the area and assess the suitability of the plantations for the research. The age of the plantation, species present, management practices, soil characteristics, and climate of the area were evaluated.

STUDY AREA

The study areas (Neem and *Eucalyptus* plantations) are inside Aliko Dangote University of Science and Technology, Wudil, Kano State, Sudan savannah

vegetation zone of Nigeria (Figure 1). The *Eucalyptus* plantations is between latitude 11°48'39"N and longitude 80°51'09"E, while the Neem plantation is between 11°48'26"N and 80°51'08"E. The altitude of the plantation varies between 401 m and 417 m above sea level, and the area sizes are 21,627 m² and 27,322 m² for Neem and *Eucalyptus* plantations, respectively. The annual rainfall and temperature range from 850 to 870 mm and 26 to 33°C, respectively. The relative humidity of the region is always low and ranges between 40% and 51.3% (Olofin et al., 2008; Kafinga et al., 2024).

Figure 1: Map of study area.

DURATION OF THE EXPERIMENT

The research was conducted for a period of four months, from June, 2023 to September, 2023.

TREE SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Stratified random sampling was used as the sampling technique of the study. In each of the two study areas, plots each measuring 20 m x 20 m were established, out of which five plots were randomly selected using a table of random numbers. The selected plots were used to measure the total height and diameter at breast height of all trees present, to be used in the allometric equation for estimating tree biomass. The sampling technique was chosen to ensure an accurate representation of the whole study area.

DIAMETER (DBH) AND HEIGHT MEASUREMENT

Diameter at breast height (DBH = 1.3 m) was measured (in cm) using a measuring tape. In contrast, the trees' total height (m) was measured using the pole method of height determination. The data collected were summarized statistically and used for

biomass estimation. The method was based on the geometric principles of similar triangles.

DENSITY OF THE TREES

The average densities of *Azadirachta indica* and *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* are 0.612 g/cm³ and 0.801 g/cm³, respectively. To determine these densities, three samples from each tree species were collected for the experiment.

The formula used for calculating density is:

$P = \text{Mass of dried wood} / \text{Volume of the wood before drying.}$

LIVE BIOMASS ESTIMATION

Above Ground Biomass

The above-ground biomass (AGB) for both species was calculated using the allometric equation developed by Chave et al. (2005), where

$$AGB = 0.0509 \times DBH^2 \times H \times p.$$

Where, DBH denotes diameter at breast height, while H is the tree height and p is the tree density.

Below Ground Biomass

The below-ground biomass (BGB) of both *Azadirachta indica* and *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* was based on findings by Mokany et al., (2006) and Walker et al. (2016), where

$$BGB = 0.26 \times AGB.$$

Total Tree Biomass

The total tree biomass (ttb) of all the tree species under research was calculated using the following formula;

$$TTB = ABG + BGB$$

TREE CARBON STOCKS (TCS)

The total live tree carbon stock of the trees was estimated by multiplying total biomass by 0.47, as recommended by (IPCC, 2006; Walker et al., 2016).

$$TCS = DM \times CF$$

Where, DM denotes the dry matter content of the tree, while CF signifies the carbon fraction of the tree biomass.

Total Carbon Dioxide Sequestered

The total carbon stock of all the tree species under investigation was converted to tones of CO₂ equivalent (tCO₂-e ha⁻¹) values by multiplying it by 44/12 or 3.67 (Pearson, Brown, and Birdsey, 2007; Ibrahim, Isah, Shamaki, 2018). This is used as a standard for reporting carbon stock estimates in the carbon market.

$$TCDS = TCS \times 3.67$$

CALCULATION OF SCALING FACTORS

When field measurements are taken within plots, a known measured area is sampled. A scaling factor is then used to extrapolate the field measurements taken (e.g. mass of

AG tree carbon within sampled plot) to a 'per hectare' basis. This scaling factor is converting the area units from square meters to one hectare:

$$S.F=10,000/400 \Rightarrow 25$$

Where:

SF = scaling factor to convert to per hectare basis (dimensionless)

10,000 = meters squared in one hectare

NA = horizontally projected area of plot (m²)

CALCULATION OF CARBON STOCK PER HECTARE

To obtain the total amount of carbon stock per hectare, all the above- and below-ground biomass from individual trees in a plot was summed and converted to carbon stock per plot, then multiplied by a scaling factor (25) to get the carbon stock per hectare.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The field data collected were subjected to calculation using the allometric equation developed by (Chave, et al., 2014). The results obtained were tabulated and summarized statistically, and then described using descriptive statistical tools such as mean, mean deviation, and coefficient of variation (CV). Besides, other inferential conclusions can also be drawn from the statistical results obtained.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research aimed to assess the biomass accumulation and carbon sequestration of *Eucalyptus* and *Azadirachta* plantations. Physical observations and visits to the study areas revealed that the Neem tree plantation has experienced significant destruction, including tree cutting and deforestation. In contrast, the *Eucalyptus* plantation is under intensive management by university stakeholders.

TREE HEIGHT H (M)

The study depicted that the maximum tree height recorded from the river red gum plantation is 27.5 m, while the minimum is 9.6 m, with an average tree height of 19.75 m. In contrast, for the Neem tree plantation, the maximum tree height is 13.30 m, with minimum and average heights of 6.7 m and 10.16 m, respectively.

DIAMETER AT THE BREAST HEIGHT DBH (CM)

Field measurement from the study proved that the widest diameter at breast height in the river red gum plantation is 45.83 cm, with a minimum and mean DBH of 13.05 cm and 32.45 cm, respectively. For the Neem tree plantation, the widest DBH was measured at 60.47 cm, while the minimum and average were recorded as 18.46 cm and 34.56 cm, respectively.

RIVER RED GUM ABOVE AND BELOWGROUND BIOMASS

It has been found from the results of the study that the maximum live above-ground biomass of a tree in a monoculture of river red gum plantation is 2,223.47 kg/tree, and the minimum is 80.47 kg/tree, with an average of 932.47 kg/tree, while the maximum

below-ground biomass is 578.10 kg/tree, with the minimum and average of 20.92 kg/tree and 242.44 kg/tree, respectively.

NEEM TREE ABOVE AND BELOW GROUND BIOMASS

A result from the study of Neem tree plantation shows that the highest aboveground biomass of a tree was found to be 1089.93 kg/tree, with the lowest and average being 81.47 kg/tree and 408.49 kg/tree, respectively. For the below-ground biomass in Neem plantation, the highest is 283.38 kg/tree, with the lowest and average being 21.18 kg/tree and 106.21 kg/tree, respectively.

TOTAL TREE CARBON STOCK PER HECTARE (TC/HA) OF RIVER RED GUM PLANTATION

The study found that the maximum tree carbon stock per hectare of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* is 493.78 tC/ha, while the minimum is 15.48 tC/ha (Figure 2). Moreover, the results show that the mean total live tree carbon stock in a hectare of river red gum in monoculture plantation with 23-25 years of age is about 172.32 tC/ha, which is much higher than the amount obtained by De Costa and Suranga (2012), who reported about 12 tC/ha to 43 tC/ha from *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* monoculture plantation with a 50-year rotation in Sri Lanka. However, the research estimated the carbon stock of different tree species, including other species of *Eucalyptus* such as *Eucalyptus grandis*, which recorded a higher carbon sequestration potential of 73-197 tC ha⁻¹, though they are better adapted to the climatic zone than *Eucalyptus camaldulensis*. This is almost the same as, or in conformity with, the result found in this research (172.32 tC/ha).

Figure 2: The relationship between DBH and TTC/ha for *Eucalyptus*.

Additionally, the result of another research study by Kumar et al. (2020) in India for *Eucalyptus tereticornis* with an 8-year rotation ranges from 114.1 Mg C ha⁻¹ to 118.8 Mg C ha⁻¹, which is lower than the result of this research, but they are very much comparable since the previous research has a much lower rotation period and uses a different allometric equation published by the Central Soil Salinity Research Institute Technical Bulletin to calculate the above-ground biomass and below-ground biomass.

Moreover, the result of this research is also comparable to a study by Zhou et al. (2017) carried out in China, which found that *Eucalyptus hybrid* (*E. urophylla* × *E. grandis*) plantation in subtropical China could have carbon storage in tree and soil (SOC) of about 299.29 tC/ha. To ensure accuracy and efficiency in the research, the report shows that destructive samples were taken and used for the development of an allometric equation specific to the species and climate, following standard operating procedure (SOP). The equation developed was used to estimate both above-ground and below-ground biomass, while the soil organic carbon (SOC) was estimated using standard methods that involve bulk density, soil carbon concentration, and soil depth.

TOTAL TREE CARBON STOCK PER HECTARE (TC/HA) OF NEEM PLANTATION

The study found that the maximum carbon storing potential of Neem tree plantation is 209.77 tC/ha and the minimum is 13.46 tC/ha (Figure 3).

Figure 3: The relationship between DBH and TTC/ha for Neem.

While the average result (67.83 tC/ha) is higher than that found by Soulé et al. (2021) in two Sahelian cities of Niger Republic, who reported that *A. indica* raised

under urban forest sequestered a mean carbon of about 26.66 ± 7.64 tC/ha in Niamey and 34.66 ± 10 tC/ha in Maradi. The study uses the allometric equation developed by Chave et al. (2014) to estimate above-ground biomass, from which the below-ground biomass was derived using by Mokany et al. (2006) recommendation (26% of AGB). In another study conducted in India by Bohre and Chaubey (2016), it was shown that *A. indica* plantation with an 18-year rotation could sequester up to about 624.21 ± 117.14 tC/ha, which is almost ten times higher than the result found in this research, though a different method of biomass estimation was used in both studies. The study uses the volume-density relationship to estimate above-ground biomass, from which carbon content was derived, while the below-ground biomass was estimated using the default value of 25% of above-ground biomass as recommended by IPCC (2006).

GENERAL RESULT DESCRIPTION

The tables (1 to 4) show a general descriptive statistical analysis of the whole study; it comprises a description of results from the two plantations (river red gum and Neem tree plantations) under study. The descriptive tools used in the research are standard deviation, standard error, variance, range, mean, maximum, minimum, and median.

Table 1: Description of the Field Data.

Blocks	No of observation	Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Median	Range
1	60	Plot	1.00	5.00	3.00	4.00
		Tree	1.00	15.00	6.50	14.00
		DBH(cm)	13.05	45.83	32.78	32.78
		H(m)	9.60	27.50	20.73	17.90
		$P(\text{g}/\text{cm}^3)$	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.00
2	53	Plot	1.00	5.00	3.00	4.00
		Tree	1.00	13.00	6.00	12.00
		DBH(cm)	18.46	60.47	34.37	42.01
		H(m)	6.70	13.30	10.50	6.60
		$P(\text{g}/\text{cm}^3)$	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.00

Table 2: Description of the Field Data.

Blocks	No of Observation	Variables	Mean	Std Dev.	Std Error	Variance
1	60	Plots	3.13	1.45	0.89	2.12
		Trees	6.80	3.89	0.50	15.14
		DBH(cm)	32.45	7.36	0.95	54.25
		PH(m)	19.75	4.43	0.56	18.67
		$P(\text{g}/\text{cm}^3)$	0.80	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	53	Plots	3.13	1.40	0.92	1.96
		Trees	6.04	3.45	0.47	11.92
		DBH(cm)	34.56	9.09	1.25	8276
		PH(m)	10.16	1.36	0.19	1.85
		$P(\text{g}/\text{cn}^3)$	0.61	0.00	0.00	0.00

Table 3: Result Summary block 1.

Blocks	No of observation	Variable	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Median	Range
1	60	AGB(kg/tree)	932.47	80.44	2223.47	858.48	2143.02
		BGB(kg/tree)	242.44	20.92	578.10	223.21	557.19

		TTB(kg/tree)	1174.92	101.36	2801.57	1081.69	2700.21
		AGCS(kgC/tree)	438.26	37.81	1045.03	403.49	1007.22
		BGBCS(kgC/tree)	113.95	9.83	271.71	104.91	261.88
		TTCS(kgC/tree)	552.21	47.64	1316.74	508.39	1269.10
		NT(/ha)	315.00	175.00	375.00	325.00	200.00
		TTCS(tC/ha)	172.34	15.48	493.78	141.07	478.29
		TCDS(tC/ha)	632.48	56.82	1812.16	517.74	1755.34
2	53	AGB(kg/tree)	408.49	81.47	1089.93	392.32	1008.46
		BGB(kg/tree)	106.21	21.18	283.38	102.00	262.19
		TTB(kg/tree)	514.69	102.65	1373.31	494.33	1270.66
		AGCS(kgC/tree)	191.99	38.29	512.27	184.39	473.97
		BGBCS(kgC/tree)	49.92	9.95	133.19	47.94	123.23
		TTCS(kgC/tree)	241.91	48.25	645.45	232.33	597.21
		NT(/ha)	276.89	200.00	325.00	275.00	125.00
		TTCS(tC/ha)	67.83	13.46	209.77	52.79	196.31
		TCDS(tC/ha)	248.93	49.41	769.87	193.73	720.45

Table 4: Result Summary block 2.

Bock	No of observation	Variable	Std dev.	Std Error	Variance	No of observation
1	60	AGB(kg/tree)	496.88	64.15	246889.77	60
		BGB(kg/tree)	129.19	16.678	16689.75	60
		TTB(kg/tree)	626.07	80.83	391962.21	60
		AGCS(kgC/tree)	233.53	30.15	54537.95	60
		BGBCS(kgC/tree)	60.72	7.84	3686.77	60
		TTCS(kgC/tree)	294.25	37.99	86584.45	60
		NT(/ha)	57.71	7.45	3330.51	60
		TTCS(tC/ha)	104.03	13.43	10823.05	60
		TCDS(tC/ha)	381.80	49.29	145774.57	60
2	53	AGB(kg/tree)	226.78	31.15	51431.62	53
		BGB(kg/tree)	58.96	8.09	3476.78	53
		TTB(kg/tree)	285.75	39.25	81652.84	53
		AGCS(kgC/tree)	106.59	14.64	11361.25	53
		BGBCS(kgC/tree)	27.71	3.81	768.02	53
		TTCS(kgC/tree)	134.30	18.45	18037.11	53
		NT(/ha)	54.46	7.49	2977.77	53
		TTCS(tC/ha)	44.78	6.15	2005.15	53
		TCDS(tC/ha)	164.34	22.57	27007.15	53

COMPARISON OF THE PLANTATIONS CARBON SEQUESTRATION ABILITY AND OBJECTIVES

As can be seen from the results, the average amount of carbon sequestered by Neem tree plantation per hectare is 67.83 tC/ha, while for river red gum plantation, it was found to be 172.34 tC/ha. Comparatively, river red gum plantation has a higher carbon sequestration ability (which is 2.54 times) than that of Neem tree plantation. Therefore, this study shows that river gum plantation sequesters more carbon compared to Neem tree plantation, and this could be attributed to the longer height of the *Eucalyptus* compared to the Neem, as well as the number of trees observed per plot.

To achieve objective one, the amount of carbon stored in a hectare of each of the plantations was used to determine the amount stored in each of the plantations under study. For river red gum plantations as a whole, it stores about 917.63 tonnes of carbon over its period (23-25 yrs) of existence, while the Neem tree plantation stores 150.17 tonnes over its period (25-30 yrs) of existence, as presented in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Comparison of the Plantations Carbon Sequestration Ability.

Sr.	Plantations	Carbon stock per hectare (tC/ha)	Amount carbon sequestered in tones	Amount tree biomass stored in tones	AGB stored in tones	BGB stored in tones
1	River red gum plantation	172.34	431.30	917.63	728.28	189.35
2	Neem tree plantation	67.83	150.17	319.51	253.58	65.93

Additionally, to achieve objective two of determining both above and below ground biomass (AGB and BGB) of the two plantations under research, the amount stored per hectare of each plantation obtained from the research computations was used to extrapolate for the whole of the plantations in question. For river red gum, it stores 728.28 tonnes and 189.35 tonnes for above and below ground biomass respectively, while the Neem stores 253.58 tonnes and 65.93 tonnes in above and below ground biomass respectively.

Besides, for objective three of the research, the carbon sequestration potential results (for both tree species/plantations) obtained from the research can serve as a tool to inform policy decisions related to carbon credits, emissions trading, or forest conservation and plantation programs. Tables 6 and 7 present the results of correlation and non-parametric correlation, respectively, between carbon sequestered by the river red gum plantation and the Neem tree plantation, as shown in the tables.

Table 6: Pearson Correlation of plants in blocks.

Sr.	Correlation	River Red Gum Tree Carbon Per Hectare	Neem Total Carbon Per Hectare
River Red Gum Tree Carbon Per 3 hectare	Pearson Correlation	1	.203
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.145
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	638559.917	50552.473
	Covariance	10823.049	972.163
	N	60	53
Neem Total Carbon Per Hectare	Pearson Correlation	.203	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.145	
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	50552.473	104267.734
	Covariance	972.163	2005.149
	N	53	53

Table 7: Correlation Coefficient of plants in blocks.

Sr.	Planatations	Corrlation	River Red Gum Tree Carbon Per Hectare	Neem Total Carbon Per Hectare
Kendall's tau_b	RIVER RED GUM TREE CARBON PER HECTARE	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.084
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.374
		N	60	53
	NEEM TOTAL CARBON PER HECTARE	Correlation Coefficient	.084	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.374	.
		N	53	53
Spearman's rho	RIVER RED GUM TREE CARBON PER HECTARE	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.121
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.387
		N	60	53
	NEEM TOTAL CARBON PER HECTARE	Correlation Coefficient	.121	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.387	.
		N	53	53

CONCLUSION

Studies related to carbon sequestration are becoming more important due to increasing pressure and concern raised about environmental protection. Globally, trees are regarded as the major terrestrial carbon sink. The study evaluated the carbon sequestration potential of Neem and river red gum plantations situated at Aliko Dangote University of Science and Technology, Wudil. The study uses the allometric equation developed by Chave et al. (2005) combined with fieldwork to compute tree densities in the study area. The results depicted that the average amount of carbon sequestered by Neem tree plantation per hectare is 67.83 tC/ha, while for river red gum plantation it is 172.34 tC/ha. Comparatively, river red gum plantation has a higher (which is 2.54 times) carbon sequestration ability than that of Neem tree plantation. Conclusively, *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* sequesters more carbon than *Azadirachta indica* over the period of time. The study shows that the plantations have made a significant contribution to carbon sequestration and, therefore, can generate carbon credits for the university and Nigeria at large. Besides, the results obtained were strongly comparable and close to those found in the related literature around the world. Such data will provide insight for prioritizing plantations for conservation and management strategies and their role as carbon sinks.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the study carried out, some recommendations have been made, as follows;

- 1-The Neem tree plantation should be reforested and managed intensively, because the low carbon sequestering potential value of the plantation is attributed due to poor management and human disturbances.
- 2- Another research should be carried out to assess the soil organic carbon stored in the plantations, which were excluded due to inefficiency of research materials and funds.

- 3- The university management should increase its involvement in forestry related researches and analysis of other options such as agroforestry in the university farms to help increase carbon storage in trees and other plants.
- 4-A research should be carried out on how to develop formulae specific to northern Nigerian climate for estimating tree biomass, for this will increase biomass estimates accuracy and precision.
- 5- The local community should be discouraged from destroying both the natural and artificial tropical forests.

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